

A FACTORIAL DESIGN OF DISTILLERS' GRAINS BASED BIOCOMPOSITES: A PATH TO SUSTAINABILITY OF CORN ETHANOL

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1 Introduction

The world population is growing. It is expected that the globe is going to accommodate more than 10 billion people in less than 40 years [1]. On the other hand, our current dependence on the depleting petroleum resources would not picture a sustainable future for the energy demand of the growing population. Thus, renewability in a reasonable period of time is a "must" for the energy sources of the future generation. The transportation sector is one of the main ones in consuming petroleum. Biofuels, i.e. biodiesel and biobased ethanol, are the renewable substituting candidates for the petroleum-based fuels with the role of gradually reducing the contribution of the petro-based fuels [2].

The biobased ethanol is predominantly produced from corn and sugar. Although the second generation biobased ethanol from lignocellulosic resources has recently emerged, it is projected that by 2020 the lignocellulosic feedstock will contribute only 4 % to the biobased ethanol production while corn and sugar will still account for the major portion (78 %) [3]. Therefore, the future of this industry is highly dependent upon the sustainability of the first generation biobased ethanol.

2 Sustainability of corn ethanol industry

In order for the corn ethanol industry to last sustainable, it is critical to create new revenue streams for it and this concept has taken the attentions towards the coproducts. In a dry mill plant and during the fermentation process, CO₂ and distillers' grains are the two main coproducts produced as much as ethanol on a weight basis [4]. As quite noticeable amount as these coproducts are produced, the revenue brought back to the ethanol industry by selling those is, however, not enough. The beverage and dry ice markets are more

beneficial to refined CO₂ suppliers than raw CO₂ producer, i.e. the ethanol plant [5]. On the other hand, distillers' grains are only used as a low cost source of nutritious value partially blended in livestock diet [4]. As far as distillers grains are concerned, the low cost of this coproduct is a great incentive to find new outlets with the aim of adding value to it.

3 Distillers' grains in polymeric composites

As a low cost filler, distillers' grains have been compounded with several polymers including thermoset [6] and thermoplastic [7-8]. The first few researches showed that the incorporation of distillers' grains, in the as-received form, to the plastic reduces almost all mechanical properties [6-7]. Thus similar to other fillers, pretreatment and/or compatibilization need to be considered for better results. For such purpose, the composition of distillers' grains should be investigated. Dried distillers grains (DDG) mainly consists of protein, fiber and lipid (oil). If it is in the form of dried distillers' grains with solubles (DDGS), the low molecular weight water-solubles also exist in a noticeable amount in the composition [8]. It is better to remove this soluble portion from DDGS if it is intended to be compounded with thermoplastics at temperatures about 180 °C. This prevents the thermal degradation of the filler to a great extent [8]. The fiber content of DDGS can lead to the modulus improvement, but at the same time the presence of protein and oil may create a plasticized phase that reduces the rigidity. With such a complexity in composition, the promising point is the presence of functional groups such as O-H and N-H in different components that can participate in chemical reaction. Therefore by choosing a proper compatibilizer, the crosslinking can happen between the distillers' grains filler and the polymeric matrix

which directly affects the mechanical performance of the composite.

We investigated this hypothesis with a polymeric isocyanate type of compatibilizer in a bioplastic/20wt%DDGS biocomposite. A biobased lubricant was also added as a processing aid. The biocomposite samples were prepared through reactive melt extrusion and injection molding. The bioplastic matrix was a commercial blend of polyhydroxy(butyrate-co-valerate), PHBV, and poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate), PBAT. Such a matrix of polyesters itself offers O-H groups suitable for crosslinking to the O-H and N-H groups of the DDGS filler as a result of the reaction with the compatibilizer.

A full factorial design of experiment (DOE) was adopted to investigate the effect of two factors, compatibilizer and lubricant, on tensile strength and impact strength. Each factor was tested in 3 levels. Addition of compatibilizer alone significantly improved both tensile and impact strength. On the other hand, addition of lubricant resulted in reduction of both responses. Also, an interaction was observed between the two factors as far as impact strength was concerned. Considering this interaction, a response surface methodology was implemented to obtain the contour plots of each response, using Minitab® software (Fig. 1). Based on the product requirements, we aimed at tensile strength of more than 20 MPa and impact strength of more than 150 J/m. The overlaid contour plots helped in finding the optimized region in which targeted value for each response is met (Fig. 2, white region).

Fig. 1. The contour plots of (a) tensile strength and (b) impact strength vs. compatibilizer and lubricant amount.

Fig. 2. Overlaid contour plots of tensile strength and impact strength vs. compatibilizer and lubricant amount.

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